

SOLVENT EXTRACTION OF ZINC FROM ACIDIC LEACH SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT. An initial test work was carried out to demonstrate that solution produced by autoclave acid leaching of Electric Arc Furnace Dust (EAFD) from the steel production could be processed through solvent extraction (SX) to recover zinc. Solvent extraction is a process for purification of the leach solution that extracts mainly zinc from other metallic impurities. To assess zinc extraction different counter-current extraction and strip configurations were tested. Extractant Di-2-ethylhexyl phosphoric acid (D2EHPA) and Shellsol D100 as a diluent were used in this investigation.

The main operational parameters and the results obtained in the test work are presented in this paper. Well over 90% of the zinc was extracted from the pregnant leach solution using multi-stage SX circuit configuration and pH adjustment. Details of circuit configurations, phase disengagement times and crud generation are also shown.

Key words: zinc, solvent extraction, circuit configuration

Introduction

Solvent extraction (SX) is a hydrometallurgical process used for the concentration and purification of the major metals such as uranium, copper, nickel and cobalt, but also for rare metals, e.g. tungsten, rare earths, thorium, vanadium, etc. (Kumar et al, 2011; Regel-Rosocka, Alguacil, 2013; Chauhan, Patel, 2014; Xie et al., 2014; Sole, Tinkler, 2016).

Technically viable solvent extraction routes also exist for zinc and it is recovered in significant quantities by the process. Di-2-ethylhexyl phosphoric acid (D2EHPA) is the most widely used extractant in the industrial practice for zinc recovery from sulphate solutions.

This extractant is selective for zinc over copper, cadmium, cobalt, nickel, etc. and is easily stripped by sulphuric acid solutions like spent electrolyte from the electrowinning (EW) process (Cole, Sole, 2002). Extraction and stripping of zinc with D2EHPA can be represented by the following reaction (Martin et al., 2002):

where:

(R – H) is the D2EHPA reagent

(ZnR₂) is the zinc-organic complex

In general, zinc SX circuit consists of the following main process steps, outlined in more details below:

- Extraction (E) - zinc containing Pregnant Leach Solution (PLS) is thoroughly mixed with an organic mixture and the zinc is selectively transferred from the aqueous to the organic phase. The organic mixture is composed of an organic reagent, called the extractant, dissolved in an essentially water-immiscible liquid hydrocarbon solvent, called the diluent.
- Washing - the zinc loaded organic phase is mixed with demineralised water to remove physically entrained halides.
- Scrubbing - the loaded organic is mixed with acidic zinc containing solution, typically diluted spent zinc electrolyte to remove co-extracted impurities from the loaded organic phase. This process step minimises the build-up of detrimental to the EW process impurities such as calcium, cadmium, copper, cobalt, nickel, etc.

- Stripping - the washed/scrubbed organic phase is contacted with an acidic aqueous solution, typically spent electrolyte from EW section and the zinc is transferred from the organic into the aqueous phase.
- Organic reagents regeneration - although selective for zinc over other metal cations, iron (III) is strongly extracted by D2EHPA. To remove iron (III) from the organic phase a bleed stream, typically 2-3% of total organic flow in the circuit, is regenerated with 6 M HCl in the this step (Musadaidzwa, Tshiningayamwe, 2009).

The SX circuit configuration is dependent on a number of variables, including the feed solution chemistry (zinc tenor, impurities and pH), strip electrolyte zinc and acid concentration, economics and operating philosophy of the plant (Soderstrom, Bednarski, 2007).

SX circuit configurations used in the industrial practice are as follows (MacKenzie, 1997):

- 2 extraction stages and 1 stripping stage (2E X 1S)
- 2 extraction stages and 2 stripping stages (2E X 2S)
- 3 extraction stages and 1 stripping stage (3E X 1S)
- 3 extraction stages and 2 stripping stages (3E X 2S)
- All of the above with additional parallel extraction (P) stage and/or washing/ scrubbing (W/Sc) stages.

Materials and methods

Pregnant Leach Solution (PLS) and Organic Phase

The zinc SX tests were carried out using zinc containing pregnant leach solution (PLS) obtained from laboratory scale autoclave acid leaching of Electric Arc Furnace Dust (EAFD), containing 22.7 % Zn. In the leach study, it was found that the material responds favourably to the process with zinc extraction of around 80%.

The optimal conditions in the leach stage were 10% solids, 65 g/l sulphuric acid, 110 °C temperature, 8 bar oxygen overpressure and 2 h leach time. The PLS (zinc SX feed) composition is shown in Table 1. The iron was removed from the zinc SX feed by precipitation using oxidation and neutralisation methods.

Solvent extraction tests were conducted with the organic phase composed of the extractant di-2-ethylhexyl phosphoric acid (D2EHPA) and the diluent ShellSol D100, both available commercially and used in various SX operations worldwide. Details of the extractant and the diluent used are given in Table 2 and Table 3 (Balesini Aghdam et al., 2011; Liu et al., 2021).

Table 1. PLS composition

Parameter	Unit	Value
pH		4.5
Na	ppm	200.5
Mg	ppm	653.2
Ca	ppm	820.8
Fe	ppm	0.142
Cu	ppm	133.6
Zn	ppm	18500
Al	ppm	368.4
Cd	ppm	40.23
Mn	ppm	968.3
Co	ppm	0.290
Ni	ppm	9.923
Pb	ppm	0.186
Cr	ppm	0.094
As	ppm	<0.01
Si	ppm	33.48
Sb	ppm	<0.01
Cl	ppm	0.110
TSS	ppm	32

Fig. 1. SX Test Apparatus

The pH values were measured with Hanna HA 2211 pH meter, while chloride concentration was determined by titration. Total suspended solids (TSS) were determined using gravimetric standard operating procedure.

Test Procedure

The SX tests were carried out in the laboratory scale apparatus, as given in Figure 1. The organic and aqueous phases were mixed at a predetermined organic to aqueous (O/A) ratio and stirred for 10 minutes. High D2EHPA concentration of 40 v/v% in the organic phase was selected in order to ensure maximum zinc transfer in the tests (Cole, Sole, 2003). The temperature was maintained at 40 °C. The emulsion was allowed to separate into two phases and the aqueous phase was removed. The pH value and the zinc content in the aqueous phase were determined. The loaded organic phase was stripped with 180 g/l H₂SO₄ solution. The experimental conditions for the SX tests are shown in Table 4:

Table 2. SX extractant characteristics

Characteristic	Unit	Value
Product name		D2EHPA
Appearance		Clear liquid
Colour		Colourless or pale yellow
Flash point	°C	150
Bis(2-ethylhexyl) hydrogen phosphate content	%	95-99
Density@20°C	kg/m ³	960-990
Viscosity@40°C	cP	21

Table 3. SX diluent characteristics

Characteristic	Unit	Value
Product name		ShellSol D100
Type		high flash, slow evaporating hydrocarbon solvent
Appearance		Liquid
Colour		Colourless
Flash point	°C	105
Density @15°C	kg/m ³	797
Viscosity@25°C	mm ² /s	3.2

Table 4. Experimental conditions for the SX tests

Characteristic	Unit	Value
Extraction O/A		1.5:1
Stripping O/A		3:1
Extractant concentration	%	40
Extraction and strip temperature	°C	40
Strip solution		180 g/l H ₂ SO ₄
Extraction and strip contact time	min	10

Equipment

Batch solvent extraction tests were performed in a laboratory scale apparatus, as given in Figure 1. The apparatus consists of 2 l glass vessel equipped with a removable stainless steel baffles (left) and a six-bladed impeller (right).

Analytical Methods

All aqueous samples were analysed for the various metal concentrations by Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES).

Results and discussion

Single Stage Extraction

To assess zinc extraction efficiency from PLS, a single stage contact was carried out by contacting the aqueous solution and organic phase with an O/A ratio of 1.5:1 for 10 minutes. The results of the experiment are shown in Table 5:

Table 5. Single Stage Extraction Results

Parameter	Unit	Value
Zn concentration in PLS	ppm	18500
pH PLS		4.5
Zn concentration in raffinate	ppm	8190
pH raffinate		0.93
Zn extraction	%	55.7

As can be seen, 55.7% of the zinc in the pregnant leach solution was extracted by the organic phase containing 40 vol.% D2EHPA in a single contact at pH value of 4.5.

Multiple Stage Extraction and Strip

For the multiple stage extraction and strip tests, 3EX2S circuit configuration was selected due to high zinc tenor in the PLS and high zinc recovery required. The circuit configuration comprises 3 extraction stages (E) and 2 stripping stages (S) as shown in Figure 2:

Fig. 2. 3EX2S circuit configuration

(PLS - Pregnant Leach Solution, LE - lean electrolyte, SE - strong electrolyte, l.o. - loaded organic, s.o. - stripped organic, E1 - first extraction stage, E2 - second extraction stage, E3 - third extraction stage, S1 - first stripping stage, S2 - second stripping stage)

Three series of multi-stage counter-current extraction and strip tests using 3EX2S circuit configuration were conducted with the main objective to achieve a zinc extraction efficiency of over 90%. The main control mechanism in the tests was the adjustment of the pH profile in the extraction stages. No pH adjustment was made in the first series, while in the other two pH was raised in E2, and E2 and E3 to ensure low levels of zinc in the raffinate. In the extraction PLS and organic phase were contacted in the test apparatus under test conditions, as given in Table 4. The pH was adjusted in the last extraction stages (E2 and E3) to around 2.5 by the addition of NaOH solution. This pH value, proposed by Pereira et al. (2007) was selected for the tests to ensure high zinc transfer and to minimise the impurities co-extraction. Samples of the PLS, aqueous effluents from E1, E2 and raffinate (E3), were taken at the end of each test and assayed for zinc to allow extraction efficiencies to be determined. The loaded organic phase was stripped in two counter-current stages S1 and S2 using sulphuric acid solution (180 g/l). Table 6, Table 7, Table 8 and Figure 3 show typical extraction efficiencies achieved during the tests.

Table 6. 3EX2S circuit configuration test results, no pH adjustment (Test Series 1)

Parameter	Unit	Value
Zn concentration in PLS	Ppm	18500
pH PLS		4.5
Zn concentration in raffinate	ppm	4350
pH raffinate		0.78
Overall Zn extraction	%	76.5

The following conclusions could be made from the results of the three test series:

- The highest overall zinc extraction efficiency of 98.2% was achieved at 3EX2S circuit configuration with pH adjustment in the extraction stages E2 and E3;

Table 7. 3EX2S circuit configuration test results, pH adjustment in the extraction stage E2 (Test Series 2)

Parameter	Unit	Value
Zn concentration in PLS	ppm	18500
pH PLS		4.5
Zn concentration in raffinate	ppm	1055
pH raffinate		1.21
Overall Zn extraction	%	94.3

Table 8. 3EX2S circuit configuration test results, pH adjustment in the extraction stages E2 and E3 (Test Series 3)

Parameter	Unit	Value
Zn concentration in PLS	ppm	18500
pH PLS		4.5
Zn concentration in raffinate	ppm	330
pH raffinate		1.64
Overall Zn extraction	%	98.2

Fig. 3. Zn Extraction Efficiency vs Zn Concentration

- Optimisation of the pH in the extraction stages is requisite for the achievement of low levels of zinc in the raffinate and for high extraction efficiency.

Key data and results from the solvent extraction test work are discussed in details below:

- The preliminary SX test work consisted of small-scale tests with pregnant leach solution (PLS) produced in the leaching of electric arc furnace dust (EAFD) to determine the zinc recoveries, phase disengagement times and eventually - crud generation.
- The analysis of the PLS (zinc SX Feed) indicates that impurity elements such as Ca, Mg, Mn, Fe, Cu and Cd would be co-extracted along with the Zn into the organic phase.
- Solvent extraction tests were conducted with the organic extractant DEHPA dissolved in ShellSol D100. The extractant used was selected considering its availability, high selectivity for zinc over Cu, Cd, Co, Ni, and the halides and effectiveness for zinc recovery from a sulphate media essentially free of ferric iron (Deep, De Carvalho, 2008).
- High DEHPA concentration of 40 v/v % in the organic phase was selected in order to ensure maximum zinc transfer in the tests.

- Approximately 56% of the zinc in the pregnant leach solution was extracted in a single stage extraction contact at pH value in the aqueous phase of 4.5.
- Approximately 76% of the zinc in the pregnant leach solution was extracted using 3EX2S circuit configuration, without pH adjustment in the extraction stages.
- The pH value in the extraction stages played a key role in achieving high zinc recoveries. pH adjustment of PLS to around 2.5 in 3EX2S circuit configuration by addition of NaOH solution gives zinc recoveries in the range of 94% - 98%.
- The extraction and stripping phase disengagement times were in the range of 60 – 90 seconds which is considered as normal.
- Phase separations were clear in all stages and no crud formation was observed.
- Further concentration and purification of the strip solution that is not however within the scope of this study, could produce an advance electrolyte, suitable for zinc electrowinning.

Conclusions

This paper presents initial experimental test work results for the recovery of zinc by solvent extraction using DEHPA as extractant from pregnant leach solution generated from leaching of electric arc furnace dust with Zn content of 18500 ppm.

The optimised 3EX2S circuit with pH adjustment in the extraction stages achieved zinc extraction and stripping efficiencies in the range of 94.3% – 98.2%.

Despite the promising results, obtained in this study, further, more detailed research work is required to optimise the organic phase composition and operating conditions, and to investigate the removal of co-extracted impurities with inclusion of washing/scrubbing stages in the SX circuit configuration.

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